

CONTINUOUS CONSOLIDATION DURING TAPE-WINDING OF HIGH PERFORMANCE THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper deals with the studying of continuous consolidation during tape-winding of high performance thermoplastic matrix composites using a hot air gun for the local welding process. After building an experimental set up, the feasibility of the process was demonstrated with glass fiber/polypropylene tape. In order to evaluate an optimum processing window, the effects of the processing parameters like temperature, winding-speed, pressure and cooling rate were experimentally investigated and discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Due to chemical and physical restrictions of thermosets usually used as matrices for high performance composites, thermoplastics are becoming of more and more interest for these purposes. Since material suppliers developed new techniques for impregnating the fibers with a thermoplastic polymer, there are different intermediate material forms available now [1] (Fig. 1). These intermediate materials also offer new techniques for the processing of laminates [2].

The subject of the present investigation is to study the continuous consolidation during winding of continuous fiber/thermoplastic tapes, using a hot air gun for the local welding process. This method is also suited using other heat-sources like infrared radiation (focused lamps, laser beams [3]), microwaves (only in dielectric active matrices) or ultrasonics. Also the automatisable tape-laying and consolidation of concav/convex or flat structures in one processing step is possible using this technique.

The welding process of thermoplastics can be described as followed:

- Heating up the materials surfaces to melt temperature,
- equalisation of the surfaces by matrix flow,
- interdiffusion of molecular chains,
- consolidation by matrix flow,
- crystallisation of semi-crystalline matrices (like polypropylene) during cooling.

The fibers affect the heating by their different thermal conductivity and capacity as well as the matrix flow processes which is favoured along the fibers rather than normal to the fiber direction. Also the crystalline structure is altered by the presence of the fibers which act as crystallite nucleators. All these processes need a definite time for reaching optimum weld strength and mechanical properties [4,5]. This is in opposite to fast processing. Therefore an experimental program was

started for better understanding of the process and to determine an optimum processing window.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Experimental set up for tape-winding

For the processing of rings or pipes by tape-winding (Fig. 2a) on a laboratory scale a common lathe with continuously variable speed is used. The mandrel is a stainless steel cylinder ($\varnothing = 100$ mm). The same kind of cylinder is used as a consolidation roller, applying the necessary pressure at the contact point by hanging different weights on levers connected to the roller (Fig. 2b). The heat is supplied by a hot air gun through a rectangular nozzle (2 mm x 30 mm). The controlled temperature is variable from 20° to 600°C, and the air volume from 3 to 300 l/min.

2. Material

The material investigated here is a pultruded continuously glass fiber reinforced polypropylene tape of 0.4 mm thickness and 13 mm width. The fiber volume fraction is $V_f = 42$ %. The crystallite melt temperature of this material was measured by DSC (differential scanning calorimetry) to $T_m = 168^\circ\text{C}$.

3. Processing

Rings consisting out of 8 wound layers were manufactured with the described method using different processing parameters. The temperature range used was from $T = 200^\circ$ up to 300°C , measured on the tape surface near the contact point and a winding-speed from $v = 1.9$ rpm (0.6 m/min) to 6.0 rpm (1.9 m/min). The pressure acting at an assumed contact length of 2 mm, was varied from $p = 5$ MPa to 12.5 MPa. In addition flat interlaminar test specimens were manufactured using the same process parameters by tape-laying instead of tape-winding.

4. Mechanical testing

Tensile hoop strength (σ_{\max}) of the wound laminate rings was obtained by quasistatic loading using the split-D-test method (Fig. 3) [6]:

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{F_{\max}}{2A} \quad (1)$$

where F_{\max} is the maximum load and A the cross-section of the ring.

To evaluate the weld quality directly, flat interlaminar test specimens were used for the DCB (double cantilever beam)-test (Fig. 4) [7]. During processing, a thin aluminium foil was placed at one end in the middle of the laminate which acts as a starter crack. The critical interlaminar fracture energy (G_{Ic}) for crack growth between two continuously welded plies was obtained by the following equation:

$$G_{Ic} = \frac{F_c^2}{2w} \cdot \frac{dC}{da} \quad (2)$$

where F_c is the critical load for macroscopic crack growth, w is the specimen-width and dC/da is the experimentally determined change of the compliance with cracklength.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Since the experiments are at the moment still in progress, the results reported here can be only preliminary. However, some constitutive results

were already obtained.

To characterize the winding process, temperature development at one point at the surface of the wound tape was determined by bonding a thermocouple to the tape (Fig. 5). The surfaces of the incoming tape and the already wound tape were preheated to the temperature of the mandrel ($T_{\text{man}} = 80^{\circ}\text{C}$), than heated up above melt temperature by the hot gas stream. The maximum was reached at the contact point (1) of the tapes where pressure was supplied by the consolidation roller. The material cooled down to the temperature of the mandrel by heat transfer to the ambient air and the already wound tape. The same point of the laminated ring was heated up during the next rounds (2-5) by thermal conduction through the thickness of the above layers. The temperature as well as heating and cooling rate decreased with the number of layers above. The big difference between the first and the second peak-temperature is due to the high heat absorption by melting the matrix in the first layer. Even for only the short time the tape surfaces were melted ($t_m \approx 2$ s), a good weld quality was obtained. The cyclic heating and cooling of the already wound layers, results in different thermal histories for the inner and outer layers. This affects the crystallite size and also the annealing of residual thermal stresses in that way, that both will decrease from the inner to the outer layers of the laminate. The laminate cross-section (Fig. 6) shows a homogenous fiber distribution without any voids in the layers. The matrix rich zones between the layers arose from the original intermediate material, the pultruded tape.

The tensile hoop strength of the manufactured rings is a fiber dominated property. The mean value obtained for well consolidated rings is $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 661 \text{ MPa} \pm 3\%$. In comparison to unidirectional glassfiber-reinforced polyphenylene sulfid filament wound rings ($\sigma_{\text{max}} = 634 \text{ MPa}$ [8], normalized for a fiber volume content of $V_f = 42\%$) this is an excellent value. Because of the nonuniform hoop stress distribution through the thickness of the rings at the gap between the D-halves (which results in interlaminar shear loads) one can expect a higher value for flat tensile test specimens. Knight [9] predict a factor of about 1.3 for the ratio of hoop stress at the inside of the ring to the averaged stress measured.

Fig. 7 shows the interlaminar fracture energy (strain energy release rate: G_{Ic}) plotted versus the processing speed. The energy required to separate the welded plies per fracture surface is $G_{\text{Ic}} = 1.2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ for speeds from $v = 0.6$ to 0.8 m/min . Faster processing results in lower values using the same process parameters ($T = 250^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p = 5 \text{ MPa}$). In comparison to molded unidirectional carbonfiber reinforced polyetheretherketone ($G_{\text{Ic}} = 2.0 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ [10]) this value is not as high, but much higher than for brittle carbonfiber/epoxy composites ($G_{\text{Ic}} = 0.2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ [10]). This is due to the bigger plastic zone size ahead of the crack tip in composites with a tough matrix, which results in a high energy absorption during a complex fracture including large ductile deformation of the matrix, fiber bridging and cracking as well as interface debonding. A micrograph of the fracture surface is shown in Fig. 8.

CONCLUSIONS

The feasibility of the continuous consolidation during tape-winding of high performance thermoplastic matrix composites using a hot air gun for the local welding process was demonstrated. Process parameters ($T = 250^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p = 5 \text{ MPa}$, $v = 0.8 \text{ m/min}$) result in well laminated rings with a tensile hoop strength of $\sigma_{\text{max}} = 661 \text{ MPa}$ and interlaminar fracture energy $G_{\text{Ic}} = 1.2 \text{ kJ/m}^2$ for unidirectional glassfiber reinforced polypropylene tape-material. The winding speed can be increased by preheating the tape

before the consolidation process.

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Fig. 1: Intermediate material forms of thermoplastic matrix composites

Fig. 2: (a) Tape-winding method (b) Experimental set up for tape-winding

Fig. 3: (a) Split-D-test-method (b) Typical load-deflection-diagram

Fig. 4: (a) DCB-test-method (b) Typical load-deflection-diagram

Fig. 5: Thermal development during tape winding

Fig. 6: Polished cross-section of a tape-wound laminate ring

Fig. 7: Interlaminar fracture energy versus processing speed
($T = 250^{\circ}\text{C}$, $p = 5 \text{ MPa}$)

Fig. 8: Interlaminar fracture surface